

DOLZARB ISSUES AND PROSPECTS IN TECHNICAL CROPS SELECTION AND SEEDING

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Abstract. *In the article, continuous professional development of managers and pedagogues based on the principle of "Learning throughout life": the relevance of innovative approaches, current problems, solutions and prospects for continuous development in the selection and breeding of technical crops for agricultural specialists it is highlighted that education is important.*

Key words: *quality education, innovative approach, pedagogical personnel, selection, seed production, technical crops, variety, hybrid, cotton, hemp, sunflower.*

Today, in the conditions of the transformation of education, there is a need to hold a scientific seminar, a scientific-practical conference or roundtable discussions on the training of leaders and pedagogues: modern trends and approaches. Continuous professional development of managers and pedagogues based on the principle of "Lifelong learning": innovative approaches are of urgent importance.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" approved on September 23, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 "Education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan - on measures to develop the fields of science" and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 23, 2019 "Additional measures to further improve the system of improving the qualifications of managers and pedagogues of higher educational institutions 797 of the Decree No. 797 of mastering, as well as improving the skills of putting into practice [1; 2; 3].

The requirements for knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences in the field of specialization will be improved based on the specific features and current issues of the direction of retraining and professional development.

In the module "Actual problems, solutions and development prospects of technical crop selection and seed breeding" module, the organizational structure of the selection-seed system in the retraining of teaching staff of higher educational institutions and their qualification improvement, directions of agricultural crop selection, On the basis of current problems of technical crop selection and seed breeding, solution and development prospects, trends in technical crop selection, innovative approaches to standardization and certification of technical crop seeds, best practices in the field, modern knowledge and skills are mastered and put into practice. the professional knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for their achievement, as well as the skills and competencies aimed at developing their creative activity will be improved.

Cultivated plants grown in order to obtain raw materials used in various types of industry (food, pharmaceutical, chemical, textile, soap, paint, perfumery, tobacco, etc.) are usually called technical.

According to their purpose, they can be divided into the following groups.

Cultivated to obtain various oils (fatty, volatile) and vegetable fiber (sunflower, castor oil, mustard, rapeseed, flax, hemp, cotton, coriander, licorice, mint, etc.) from oil and spinning plants.

Medicinal and alkaloidal plants are needed in the food, pharmaceutical, chemical and other industries (tobacco, Jerusalem artichoke, chicory, naperstyanka, valerian, chamomile, etc.).

Sugar and starch plants are used to produce sugar and starch (beets and potatoes).

The inclusion of technical plants in crop rotation serves to increase the general culture of agriculture and the productivity of other field crops. The reason is that most of them (sunflower, sugar beet, potato, etc.) are tillage crops and require to keep the rows softened and free of weeds. In these fields, as a rule, they are well cultivated and fertilizers are used in high doses.

Waste oil is widely used as fodder or fertilizer in sugar beet, starch, brewing and many other industries. Some technical plants are also used for fodder purposes (sunflower, rapeseed, mustard and green fodder and silage, potatoes, sugar beets, etc.).

In the cultivation of technical crops, intensive agricultural technologies are used more than other field crops (the most modern varieties and hybrids, specialized machinery, optimization of mineral nutrition, irrigation, highly effective chemical plant protection agents, etc.).

In our republic, cotton (*Gossypium L.*) is the most cultivated crop among technical crops. Today, varieties of cotton such as Sultan, Bukhara 6, Bukhara 8, An-Bayavut-2, S-6524, Porloq-4, Andijan-37, Khorezm-127, S-4727 are cultivated in large areas [4]. In addition, more than 20 promising and more than 40 regional varieties of agricultural crops recommended for planting in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan are included in the State Register and are being cultivated in different soil and climate regions of the country. It is necessary to continuously continue the research on the problems and their solutions in the field of cotton seed production [5; 6].

Another technical crop is hemp (*Hibiscus cannabinus*), which has 4 varieties in the state register. These varieties are Uzbekskiy 1972, Uzbekskiy 2142, Uzbekistan 225, Uzbekistan 2268 [4]. It is not advisable to plant hemp in one area for more than two years. According to the recommendation of our scientists, good productivity is achieved when the alfalfa-wheat-cotton-hemp alternating cropping system is planted in the field, i.e. hemp for 2 years, alfalfa for 3 years and cotton and other agricultural crops for 4 years. Navbatdagi texnik ekinlardan tamaki (*Nicotiana tabacum L.*) ning mamlakatimizda ekilib kelinayotgan va Davlat reyestrída mavjud bo'lgan 4 ta navi-Basma, Virdjiniya-1, Dyubek 44-07, Izmir navlari bor [4].

Apart from cotton, sunflower (*Helianthus annus L.*) cultivars and hybrids are more numerous in the State Register, i.e. more than 50, among technical crops in our republic. Albatros F1, Adazi F1, Buzuluk, Berezansky, Dilbar and Diyor are among them [4].

In addition to the technical crops mentioned above, there are a number of varieties of potatoes and beets in our republic. But there are very few varieties of castor oil, mustard, rapeseed, flax, hemp, coriander, licorice, mint, Jerusalem artichoke, chicory, valerian, chamomile and other technical crops. Taking into account that technical crops are widely used by the population, it is necessary to use new innovative technologies and new methods to create new varieties of them. It is necessary to continue research in this regard.

REFERENCES:

1. Yakubjonova, n., & sherboyev, s. (2023). Sabzavot loviyasi kolleksiya nav namunalari oqsil miqdorining tahlili. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(4), 111-115.

2. Barotova A., Raxmatullayev S., Ismoilova A. DEFINING THE SEED FIBER RESIDUE AND WEIGHT OF 1000 SEEDS IN COTTON VARIETIES //Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 22-25.

3. Barotova A. et al. EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS //Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 41-46.

4. Quvondiqovich, M. B., Ruzievna, K. G., Abduganievich, E. J., Turdikulovich, J. S., Razzakovna, B. A., & Erkinovna, S. G. (2020). Performance Of Fiber Output And Fiber Length In Inter Variety Hybrid Families Of Middle Fiber Cotton. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.

5. Jo'rayev, S. T., Ashurov, M., Narmatova, G., Toreev, F., Akhmedov, D., Mavlonova, N., ... & Baratova, A. (2022). Cotton breeding and seed production. *LESSON PRESS*, 1(1), 224.

6. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Raxmatullayev, S., & Ismoilova, A. (2023). EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(2), 41-46.

7. Ergashev, J., Kholmurodova, G., Egamberdiev, R., & Barotova, A. (2023, February). Fiber Consumption and Quality Indicators of Varieties of *G. Hirsutum L.* Type and Interspecific Hybrid Combinations. In *XV International Scientific Conference "INTERAGROMASH 2022" Global Precision Ag Innovation 2022, Volume 2* (pp. 2187-2192). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

8. Баротова, А. Р., Якубжоновна, Н. А., & Хуррамов, А. А. (2022). ФЎЗА НАВЛАРИ СЕЛЕКЦИЯСИДА ҚИММАТЛИ ХЎЖАЛИК БЕЛГИЛАРНИНГ ИРСИЙЛАНИШИ, ЎЗГАРУВЧАНЛИГИ ВА ШАКЛЛАНИШИ. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 318-321.

9. Razzokovna, B. A. (2022). G 'O 'ZA OILALARIDA SELEKSIYASIDA QIMMATLI XO 'JALIK BELGI KO'RSATKICHLARINING O'ZGARUVCHANLIGI VA SHAKLLANISHI. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(13), 479-481.

10. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Mamadaliyev, A. B., & Jo'rayev, O. (2023). INHERITANCE, VARIABILITY AND FORMATION OF FERTILITY ELEMENTS IN COTTON. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(3), 20-23.

11. Kholmurodova, G., Barotova, A., Namazov, S., Yuldasheva, R., & Jumashev, M. (2023, January). Creation of selected items with high fiber yield and length based on cotton composite hybrids. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 371, p. 01039).

12. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Mamadaliyev, A. B., & Jo'rayev, O. (2023). FIBER LENGTH AND QUALITY INDICATORS IN COTTON VARIETIES. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(3), 50-53.

14. Kholmurodova, G. R., Mirkhomidova, N. A., Yuldasheva, R. A., Nazarova, M. B., Barotova, A. R., & Aktamova, I. A. (2023, March). Creation of goods with high fiber quality from the selection of varieties belonging to *G. Hirsutum L.* species. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1142, No. 1, p. 012089). IOP Publishing.

15. Kholmurodova, G. R., Yuldasheva, R. A., Barotova, A. R., Yakubjanova, N. A., Khakimova, M. M., & Aktamova, I. A. (2023, March). Correlation between family and range value

economic traits in cotton. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1142, No. 1, p. 012075). IOP Publishing.

16. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Raxmatullayev, S., & Ismoilova, A. (2023). EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(2), 41-46.

17. Kholmurodova, G., Barotova, A., Namazov, S., Yuldasheva, R., & Jumashev, M. (2023, January). Creation of selected items with high fiber yield and length based on cotton composite hybrids. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 371, p. 01039).

18. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Ismoilov, I., & Yigitaliyeva, M. (2023). TOLERANCE OF NEWLY CREATED RIDGES TO CERTAIN BIOTIC FACTORS, MORPHO-ECONOMY AND FIBER QUALITY INDICATORS. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(4), 49-52.

19. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Mamadaliyev, A. B., & Jo'rayev, O. (2023). INHERITANCE, VARIABILITY AND FORMATION OF FERTILITY ELEMENTS IN COTTON. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(3), 20-23.

20. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Ismoilov, I., & Yigitaliyeva, M. (2023). TOLERANCE OF NEWLY CREATED RIDGES TO CERTAIN BIOTIC FACTORS, MORPHO-ECONOMY AND FIBER QUALITY INDICATORS. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(4), 49-52.

21. Xurramov, A., Muydinov, R. X., & Barotova, A. (2023). STUDYING BRANCHING AND ITS TYPES IN THE COTTON VARIETIES. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(5), 20-23.

22. Razokovna, B. A. (2023). Go'zaning G. hirsutum L. va G. barbadense L. turlariga mansub boshlang'ich ota-ona shakllarining morfo-xo'jalik belgilarining tahlili. *IQRO JURNALI*, 1(2), 162-165.

23. Kholmurodova, G., Barotova, A., Yuldasheva, R., & Mirkhamidova, N. Formation of yield elements in composite hybrid families of cotton. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 389, p. 03092). EDP Sciences.

24. yakubjonova, n. (2023). General factors of the development of the science of biology and genetics in higher educational institutions. *International bulletin of medical sciences and clinical research*, 3(3), 52-54.

25. abdullayeva, b., & yakubjonova, n. (2023). Typological features of combining biology and genetics based on an integrative approach. *International bulletin of medical sciences and clinical research*, 3(3), 39-41.

26. Juraev, s. T., & yakubjonova, n. A. (2022). Analysis of value-economic characteristics of introgressive hybrids of cotton under different soil-climate conditions in uzbekistan. *Galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal*, 10(12), 1638-1646.

28. azizov, b. M., jumashev, m. M., yakubjonova, n. A., & khayrullayev, s. (2021). Effect of sowing rate on the quality of seeds of winter wheat. *Theoretical & applied science учредители: теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 755-760.

29. azizov, m. B., aberkulov, m. N., yakubjonova, n. A., & khayrullayev, s. S. (2021). Efficiency of mixed sowing of maize with forage beet in irrigated meadow sierozem soils of uzbekistan. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(8), 316-320